

An LLM-based Architecture for Socially Intelligent Robot Navigation based on Social Cues

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Abstract—The integration of robots into human-shared environments has driven advancements in social robotics and natural Human-Robot Interaction. A key challenge in this field is to enable robots to interpret and respond to social cues, ensuring fluid, context-aware, and socially acceptable interactions. To address this, we propose a two-layer architecture for social navigation. The high-level reasoning layer utilizes Large Language Models to interpret contextual and environmental cues, generating constraints for navigation. These constraints are then enforced by the low-level layer, which employs Control Barrier Functions to ensure smooth and socially compliant robot movements. We validate our approach in a dynamic simulation environment, demonstrating effective constraint enforcement and socially acceptable navigation behavior.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the use of robotics in environments shared with humans has been increasing. Whether for assisting in daily tasks or industrial applications, robots have been integrated into social contexts involving human interaction, driving research on social robotics and smart and natural Human-Robot Interaction (HRI).

One of the key challenges in this field is enabling robots to assist people beyond the limits of traditional robotics expertise and to effectively understand and respond to human and social cues, a process known as social perception [1], [2]. For successful interaction with humans and an appropriate response to their requests and needs, service robots should recognize and comprehend their interlocutor. This requires the development of intelligent systems capable of engaging with users in a fluid and context-aware manner, responding to social cues such as gestures, body language, verbal and non-verbal stimuli, and spatial positioning.

As many other fields, the rise of artificial intelligence (AI) also impacted the HRI domain. In particular, the integration of Large Language Models (LLMs) with robotic systems has introduced a transformative paradigm, providing unprecedented capabilities in natural language understanding and task execution [3]. Beyond perception, LLMs can be used to score potential next actions and even generate action sequences directly from natural language instructions, without requiring additional domain-specific knowledge. Several

Fig. 1: Social robot operating into a human-shared scenario.

research efforts have leveraged these capabilities to improve robotic perception, planning, and decision-making in dynamic environments, exploring different methodologies to improve interaction and adaptation. For instance, the LLM-GROP approach, presented in [4], focuses on extracting commonsense knowledge from LLMs to infer semantically valid object configurations and integrate them with task and motion planning to generalize to varying scene geometry. In [5], the authors proposed a method to personalize household cleanup by learning user preferences for object placement. Their approach uses language-based planning and few-shot learning with LLMs to infer generalized preferences from limited interactions. This enables robots to adapt quickly to different users and apply learned preferences to future tasks.

More related to the social navigation domain, in [6], the authors proposed a novel hybrid approach called Socially-Aware navigation Large Language Model framework (SALM), which integrates LLM and Deep Reinforcement Learning to navigate through human-filled public spaces and provide multiple social services. SALM infers global planning from human-in-the-loop commands in real-time, and encodes social information into a LLM-based large navigation model for low-level motion execution.

To ensure safe and adaptive navigation in human-populated environments, mobile robots must go beyond collision avoidance by adjusting their social behaviors when approaching people [7]–[9]. In scenarios like intersections or narrow doorways, they need to resolve deadlocks by either taking the initiative to move first or signaling users to pass [10]. Additionally, robots may need to follow or accompany individuals [11]–[13]. This requires keeping users within their field of view [14], recognizing individuals, adapting their speed based on personal preferences [15], and stopping if the user is no longer present [16].

Despite the growing use of LLMs across various sectors, enabling service robots to perceive and interpret contextual

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and environmental cues remains an open research challenge. This capability would allow robots to act as socially intelligent agents, adapting their actions to the social context (Fig. 1). For example, a robot could accompany a user, follow them to a destination, or approach a group interested in interacting. Understanding the operational context would also enable robots to consider social and psychological factors, such as maintaining appropriate interpersonal distance based on emotional state or adjusting speed to match the user’s age and mobility.

In this work, we propose a two-layer architecture that modulates navigation constraints for a social robot based on its operating environment: i) the high-level reasoning layer uses LLMs to perceive contextual and environmental cues from the social context. Based on this information, the LLMs generate low-level constraints that guide the robot’s navigation, ensuring its movements are natural and socially acceptable. For example, social factors such as the required distance the robot must maintain from the user and its maximum allowable speed influence navigation decisions. Additionally, the robot’s navigation mode, categorized as reach, follow, or accompany, is dynamically adjusted according to the surrounding context; ii) the low-level layer handles navigation using Control Barrier Functions (CBFs) as a reactive method. Using a reactive approach, the service robot can dynamically adjust its control, ensuring smooth and socially acceptable interactions with users. Leveraging the high-level reasoning layer, the low-level navigation system incorporates social constraints, enhancing user safety and acceptance of the robot’s behavior.

II. PRELIMINARIES

As already stated, the proposed architecture consists of two main components: a high-level reasoning layer, where LLMs interpret the surrounding context, and a low-level execution layer, where the CBF framework enables reactive and socially acceptable navigation. LLMs, widely used in robotics, automation, and interactive systems, generate and interpret human-like text and support structured decision-making. A key feature is Function Calling (FC), which enhances their utility by enabling structured outputs that external systems can execute. This ensures responses adhere to predefined formats, improving reliability—an essential aspect for tasks like robotic navigation.

In this context, LLMs can be represented as a function approximation: $f_\phi : \mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathcal{T}$ where f_ϕ is the LLM function parameterized by ϕ (the actual domain), \mathcal{P} is the space of natural language prompts, \mathcal{S} is the set of the functions schema, \mathcal{T} is the space of possible structured text outputs. Given a function schema s (e.g., the robot function to call) and a natural language prompt p , the LLM function generates a mapping $f_\phi(p, s) \rightarrow t^*$, where $t^* \in \mathcal{T}_S$, the subset of outputs conforming to \mathcal{S} . The structured output t^* is parsed into a function call: $q : \mathcal{T}_S \rightarrow \mathcal{E}$ where \mathcal{E} is the set of executable robot operations, which finally maps the selected function to call to a specific robot behavior.

As for the low-level control, the set of real numbers is denoted by \mathbb{R} , and \mathbb{R}^n represents the n -dimensional real vector space. The set of non-negative and positive real numbers are $\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ and $\mathbb{R}_{> 0}$, respectively. Regarding the CBF formulation, let $x \in \mathcal{D} \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and $u \in \mathcal{U} \subset \mathbb{R}^m$ be the state and input of a nonlinear input-affine control system:

$$\dot{x} = f(x) + g(x)u, \quad (1)$$

for which the compact set \mathcal{U} contains the feasible control values and in which $f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ and $g : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ are assumed to be locally Lipschitz functions. We desire a given safe set $\mathcal{C} \subset \mathcal{D} \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ to be forward invariant for the system, that is, $\forall x(0) \in \mathcal{C}, x(t) \in \mathcal{C} \forall t \geq 0$. This property ensures that the specified set remains forward invariant with respect to the system’s dynamics. Consequently, if the system starts within this set, it will always stay within it [17]. The forward invariance of the safe set can be achieved by means of the definition of the CBF.

Following CBF theory [17]–[19], let $\mathcal{C} = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n : h(x) \geq 0\}$ be the set of configurations that satisfy the safety requirements for the system, also known as the safe set \mathcal{C} , which is defined as the super level set of a smooth function $h : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with $\frac{\partial h}{\partial x}(x) \neq 0 \forall x \in \partial \mathcal{C}$, where $\partial \mathcal{C} = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n : h(x) = 0\}$. CBFs are defined by the following relation, considering an extended class \mathcal{K} function α such that for the system (1) and for all $x \in \mathcal{C}$:

$$\exists u \text{ s.t. } \dot{h}(x, u) \geq -\alpha(h(x)) \Leftrightarrow \mathcal{C} \text{ is forward invariant.}$$

With this condition it is possible to set up an optimization-based control problem that modifies the desired control input $u_{des} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ and the actuated one so that the latter satisfies the CBF constraint, solving the following optimization problem:

$$u(x) = \underset{u \in \mathcal{U}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \frac{1}{2} \|u - u_{des}\|^2 \quad (2a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \dot{h}(x, u) \geq -\alpha(h(x)). \quad (2b)$$

When dealing with multiple barrier functions, it is possible to utilize a smooth approximation of the min operator [8] in order to approximate the set of all barriers into a single one, thus obtaining the most constraining barrier function. For k barrier functions $h_l : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ where $l \in \{1, \dots, k\}$, let

$$h^*(x) := -\frac{1}{\eta} \ln \left(\sum_{l=1}^k \exp(-\eta h_l(x)) \right) \quad \text{with } \eta > 0. \quad (3)$$

Note that $\min_{l \in \{1, \dots, k\}} h_l(x) \approx h^*(x)$ where the precision of this approximation improves as η increases. This is beneficial because, if $h^*(x) \geq 0$, it ensures that $h_l(x) \geq 0$ for each $l \in \{1, \dots, k\}$.

Along with navigation constraints, another important element regards the social zones. Social norms, often implicit and unspoken, are challenging to define and implement in robotics. When robots move to avoid humans, it is important to ensure not only physical safety, which prevents collisions, but also psychological safety, which avoids causing disturbance or discomfort to people [20]. Proximity plays a

Fig. 2: Human social interaction space.

key role in avoidance behaviors, with research on proxemics examining personal space, a fundamental aspect of social convention that, when invaded, can cause discomfort.

Using the procedure exposed in [21] and considering a and b as generic Cartesian coordinates, the human social interaction space is modeled as a two-dimensional asymmetric Gaussian function, $f(a, b) : \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{>0}$, centered at the user's position (x_H, y_H) , which is determined as follows:

$$f(a, b) = e^{-\left(\frac{(d \cos(\gamma))^2}{2\sigma_a^2} + \frac{(d \sin(\gamma))^2}{2\sigma_b^2}\right)}, \quad (4)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} d &= \sqrt{(a - x_H)^2 + (b - y_H)^2}, \\ \theta &= \text{atan2}((b - y_H), (a - x_H)), \\ \theta^{po} &= \text{rotation of the function } f \text{ minus } \frac{\pi}{2}, \\ \gamma &= \theta - \theta^{po}, \text{ converted in } (-\pi, \pi]. \end{aligned}$$

The values of σ_a and σ_b in (4) vary among $\sigma_l, \sigma_h, \sigma_s$ and σ_r according to γ in the four different quadrants, as shown in Fig. 2. Thus, by arbitrarily choosing l_r , the length of the square representing the intimate zone of a human, and the values of d_i , according to [21], the four variances $\sigma_l, \sigma_h, \sigma_s$ and σ_r for the function $f(a, b)$ are calculated as follows:

$$\sigma_i = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{(d_i + 0.5l_r)^2}{\ln 10}}, \text{ with } i = \{l, h, s, r\}. \quad (5)$$

III. FROM SOCIAL CUES TO NAVIGATION

Consider a scenario where a robot navigates a social environment with static obstacles (e.g., objects, stationary individuals) and dynamic ones (e.g., moving people). The robot has access to contextual and environmental data, including user IDs, preferences, positions, and map data. As illustrated in Fig. 4, the proposed architecture enables the high-level reasoning layer to interpret social cues and adapt navigation accordingly. If certain information is unavailable, the robot retrieves it from a dedicated database (as shown in [2]). The high-level layer also determines the appropriate navigation mode by adjusting low-level navigation constraints. In particular, we consider the different scenarios where a user might need to reach a target position, be accompanied by the robot or be followed by the robot. To this end, we introduce

Fig. 3: Simulated scenario in Gazebo: the robot performs navigation tasks while adhering to social navigation constraints. The environment also includes three static obstacles (red) and a door (black).

three navigation modes, which we name reach, accompany, or follow. To ensure socially acceptable behavior, the robot should maintain greater distance from users who appear uncomfortable and dynamically adjusts its speed based on user characteristics, moving faster with younger individuals and slower with elderly or impaired users.

System Architecture: Referring to the architecture diagram shown in Fig. 4, after the user request for robot assistance, depicted in orange, the high-level reasoning layer, highlighted in red, processes the request along with contextual and environmental cues extracted from the robot's operational area. This layer then generates specific outputs via FC, which are subsequently passed to the low-level layer, marked in blue. The low-level layer employs CBFs to ensure smooth and socially acceptable behaviors while adhering to social navigation constraints, such as collision avoidance, velocity limits, and angular constraints. Furthermore, this layer continuously detects obstacles around the robot using the *check_obstacles* block and determines the optimal goal pose when the robot is instructed to reach an individual or a group using the *check_goal_pose* block.

High-level reasoning: Although the architecture conceptually allows for the integration of various types of contextual and environmental cues, our implementation specifically employs those highlighted in yellow in Fig. 4. Following the user's input request and the considered social cues, the high-level reasoning layer performs an initial FC request to determine whether the user intends to initiate a conversation with the robot, be accompanied, be followed, or be reached at a specific location. Such FC request is implemented through the *request_context* mentioned in Tab. I, which contains sample prompts specifying the robot context used in the FC processes.

Following a human request, the high-level layer performs different queries to assess first the contextual information and later the task to accomplish. In the first step, the robot relies on the LLM engine to update some specific parameters of the interacting user. In particular, based on the robot database and possible sensor input, the LLM engine of the architecture retrieves fundamental information for the social intelligent navigation. In the specific case of this work, we

Fig. 4: Proposed system architecture: high-level reasoning layer (red) and low-level layer (blue).

considered the following parameters: the user id or their name; the user’s category, classified as either slow (e.g., elderly individuals or people with impairments) or fast (e.g., young individuals); the confidence score, a numeric value indicating the user comfort with robotic systems; the user’s current position, speed and target destination. Each field can be set to and unknown value if the corresponding information is unavailable.

Next, by exploiting the information retrieved about the user and contextual environment, and the explicit received request, the LLM executes a series of FC requests, using the functions illustrated in Fig. 4. The FC outputs are mapped to specific robot behaviors, as outlined in Sec. II, and then passed to the low-level layer of the architecture. These outputs include: i) the navigation mode, choosing between reach, accompany and follow; ii) the robot maximum speed, related to the context included in Tab. I, by providing the LLM system with the *robot maximum speed context*. This value will be applied in the reach and accompany modes, while, in the follow mode, the robot will use the human speed parameter as its maximum speed; iii) the social zone distance, by providing the LLM with the *social zone distance context* (see Tab. I), based on Hall’s social zone and proximity distance definitions [21]. This distance varies depending on the detected confidence score of the user. It is used in the reach mode to determine the robot’s goal pose and in the accompany and follow modes to set the distance the robot should maintain from the user during the task. Additionally, this parameter is used as d_h to compute σ_h in (5), which determines how far the robot should position itself in front of the user. Meanwhile d_l , d_s and d_r are considered fixed, as a mobile robot positioned behind or to either side of a human is generally less dangerous than one in front at the same distance, as reported in [21].

TABLE I: LLM system prompts list

request context
<p>You are a robot navigation assistant. You know information about the most engaged user parameters: $\{json.dumps(most_engaged_user.model_dump())\}$ and the actual LLM output parameters: $\{json.dumps(llm_output.model_dump())\}$. Based on the context of the user’s request, you are able, by utilizing the available tools $\{tools\}$, to provide various outputs such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The parameters needed to accompany a specific user in json format. • The parameters needed to reach a specific user in json format. • The parameters needed to follow a specific user in json format. • Reset the context when the interaction with the user is finished. • Provide the chat history. • Otherwise, answers to generic questions.
robot maximum speed context
<p>You are a robot navigation assistant with the following strict adherence rule: - Reply only in the following format:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • robot maximum speed: $\langle value \rangle [m/s]$ • short explanation of the reasoning <p>You have access to information about the user’s category parameter: $\{json.dumps(most_engaged_user.model_dump())\}$. Your task is to determine the robot maximum speed following these rules:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The robot maximum speed for the robot is a float value between $0.1[m/s]$ and $0.8[m/s]$. • If the user is Fast: the robot can move at a faster speed, prioritizing efficiency and responsiveness. • If the user is Slow: the robot should move at a moderate speed to ensure safety and comfort. • If the user is Impaired: the robot should prioritize safety and move at a slow speed. • If the user’s state is unclear, unspecified, or unknown, use the default robot maximum speed of $0.5[m/s]$.
social zone distance context
<p>You are a robot navigation assistant with the following strict adherence rule: - Reply only in the following format:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • social zone distance: $\langle value \rangle [m]$ • short explanation of the reasoning <p>You have access to information about the user’s confidence parameter: $\{json.dumps(most_engaged_user.model_dump())\}$.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A high confidence value indicates that the user is likely to prefer closer interaction with the robot. • A low confidence value indicates the user may prefer more distance. <p>The social zone distance is a float value between $1.0[m]$ and $1.4[m]$. Your task is to determine the appropriate social zone distance based solely on the user’s confidence state, following these guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Choose a smaller distance (closer to $1.0[m]$) if the user feels comfortable (e.g., confident, relaxed, open, calm, secure, reassured). • Choose a larger distance (closer to $1.4[m]$) if the user feels uncomfortable (e.g., anxious, nervous, afraid, suspicious, restless, tense, worried, hesitant, defensive). • If the user’s state is unclear, unspecified, or unknown, default the social zone distance to $1.2[m]$.

The high-level reasoning layer is designed to retain user input requests relevant to the same context within the LLM’s chat history. This prevents information loss, enhancing the robustness of the architecture. For instance, if a user initially requests to be followed into a specific location (e.g., the kitchen) but later the robot perceives discomfort or confusion by the user, the high-level layer adjusts the navigation parameters accordingly by leveraging the historical context of the interaction. However, when the context—and thus the interacting user—changes, the layer resets the chat history.

Navigation framework: The low-level layer is used as a navigation framework to perform reach, follow, and accompany tasks through the use of CBFs. Receiving input parameters from the high-level reasoning layer enables the low-level layer to execute smooth robot movements with socially acceptable behaviors while adhering to social navigation constraints. In particular, the navigation framework is defined by the optimization problem in (6), where collision avoidance, velocity constraints, and angular constraints are considered as social navigation constraints, as expressed in (6b).

The control input $u \in \mathbb{R}^2$, representing the velocity components $v_x \in \mathbb{R}$ and $v_y \in \mathbb{R}$, is computed with reference to the optimization problem in (2) as:

$$u(x), \delta = \underset{u \in \mathcal{U}, \delta \in \mathbb{R}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \frac{1}{2} \|u - u_{des}\|^2 + m\delta^2 \quad (6a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \dot{h}_{obs}^*(x, u) \geq -\alpha(h_{obs}^*(x)),$$

$$\|v_x + v_y\| \leq v_{max}, \quad (6b)$$

$$\dot{h}_{fov}(\mathcal{R}p_{\mathcal{H}}, u) \geq -\alpha(h_{fov}(\mathcal{R}p_{\mathcal{H}})) - \delta.$$

Here, the desired control input $u_{des} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ is designed to drive the system toward the target position $x_{tgt} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ relative to the current robot pose $x_{act} \in \mathbb{R}^2$, which corresponds to the first two components of the state $x \in \mathbb{R}^3$. Thus, u_{des} is computed as: $u_{des} = K(x_{tgt} - x_{act})$, where $K \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ is a proportional gain. Moreover, we consider a slack variable $\delta \in \mathbb{R}$ with a slack variable weight $m \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ in order to relax the angular constraint in cases where the constraint cannot be strictly satisfied due to system limitations (e.g., the use of a differential-drive robot).

Within the navigation framework, the *check_obstacles* module is responsible for continuously elaborating the laser scan data of the robot, generating a list of detected obstacle positions, $x_{obs} \in \mathbb{R}^2$, at a certain distance from it. For a given obstacle i , approximated as a circle with radius $R_i \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$, the collision avoidance constraint can be satisfied by defining the barrier function: $h_{obs}(x) = \|x_{act} - x_{obs_i}\|^2 - R_i^2$. The function $h_{obs}(x)$ is a CBF if the control input u ensures that $\dot{h}_{obs}(x, u) = 2(x_{act} - x_{obs_i})u \geq \alpha(h_{obs}(x))$. Thus, the most constraining barrier function $h_{obs}^*(x)$ can be defined using a smooth approximation of the min operator (3), leading to the constraint formulation in (6b).

Regarding the non-linear velocity constraint, given the robot maximum speed parameter, $v_{max} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$, provided by the high-level reasoning layer, the constraint is imposed by ensuring that the squared norm of the velocity satisfies $\|v_x + v_y\| \leq v_{max}$ as expressed in (6b).

Exploiting the methodology presented in [14], [19], the FOV constraint in (6b) can be defined. Specifically, considering \mathcal{W} as the world reference frame, \mathcal{R} as the local robot reference frame, and \mathcal{H} as the local human reference frame, the FOV constraint is formulated based on the relative position of the detected user, represented by the components ${}^{\mathcal{W}}x_H$ and ${}^{\mathcal{W}}y_H$, with respect to the robot state $x = [{}^{\mathcal{W}}x, {}^{\mathcal{W}}y, {}^{\mathcal{W}}\theta]$. This relationship is expressed as:

$$\mathcal{R}p_{\mathcal{H}} = [{}^{\mathcal{W}}x_H - {}^{\mathcal{W}}x, {}^{\mathcal{W}}y_H - {}^{\mathcal{W}}y]^T.$$

Next, the constraint is split into two components that are treated as different constraints entered into an optimization solver. To this end, we introduce the following $h_{fov}(\cdot)$ for the robot:

$$h_{fov}(\mathcal{R}p_{\mathcal{H}}) = \begin{bmatrix} h_1(\mathcal{R}p_{\mathcal{H}}) \\ h_2(\mathcal{R}p_{\mathcal{H}}) \end{bmatrix} = \lambda \begin{bmatrix} \tan(\frac{\beta}{2}) & 1 \\ \tan(\frac{\beta}{2}) & -1 \end{bmatrix} \mathcal{R}p_{\mathcal{H}}. \quad (7)$$

Imposing the condition $h_{fov}(\cdot) \geq [0, 0]^T$ is equivalent to constraining the robot's orientation such that the user remains within the angular FOV β . The parameter λ takes a value of -1 if the constraint is applied behind the robot in accompany mode, or 1 during the reach and follow modes. The time derivative of (7) is then expressed as:

$$\dot{h}_{fov}(\mathcal{R}p_{\mathcal{H}}, u) = \frac{\partial h_{fov}(\mathcal{R}p_{\mathcal{H}})}{\partial \mathcal{R}p_{\mathcal{H}}} \mathcal{R}\dot{p}_{\mathcal{H}} = \lambda \begin{bmatrix} \tan(\frac{\beta}{2}) & 1 \\ \tan(\frac{\beta}{2}) & -1 \end{bmatrix} \mathcal{R}\dot{p}_{\mathcal{H}},$$

where the velocity of human with respect to the robot, $\mathcal{R}\dot{p}_{\mathcal{H}}$, is then expressed through kinematic computations:

$$\mathcal{R}\dot{p}_{\mathcal{H}} = \mathcal{R}R_{\mathcal{W}} {}^{\mathcal{W}}\dot{p}_{\mathcal{H}} - \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{R}v_x \\ \mathcal{R}v_y \end{bmatrix} + \omega \begin{bmatrix} {}^{\mathcal{W}}y_H - {}^{\mathcal{W}}y \\ -({}^{\mathcal{W}}x_H - {}^{\mathcal{W}}x) \end{bmatrix},$$

considering the rotation matrix $\mathcal{R}R_{\mathcal{W}}$:

$$\mathcal{R}R_{\mathcal{W}} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos({}^{\mathcal{W}}\theta) & \sin({}^{\mathcal{W}}\theta) \\ -\sin({}^{\mathcal{W}}\theta) & \cos({}^{\mathcal{W}}\theta) \end{bmatrix}.$$

Within the navigation framework, the social zone distance parameter regulates the robot's interaction with humans across different navigation modes. In the reach mode, it determines the optimal position for the robot to approach the interacting user based on their location and orientation, following the procedure described in [9]. In the accompany mode, this parameter ensures that the robot does not advance toward the target destination if the distance between the robot and the user exceeds the predefined social zone distance. Finally, in the follow mode, it prevents the robot from approaching the user beyond the social zone distance.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

To validate the proposed architecture, we conducted Gazebo simulations with a differential-drive robot operating at 50 Hz in a social environment, populated with different users and unknown static obstacles, as shown in Fig. 3 and in the accompanying video¹. As LLM engine, we considered the *llama3.1:8b* and *command-7rb* models.

In the considered scenario, the goal of the robot is to assist the users to satisfy their requests. To demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed approach, we defined two different use cases: i) reach: based on the environmental and social cues, the regulation in the reaching behavior of the robot towards a specific user is assessed; ii) follow-accompany: the capacity of the robot to infer the correct navigation mode, modulating it based on sequential human requests is demonstrated. Finally, to further evaluate the performance of the high-level reasoning layer, we assessed the system's

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TABLE II: Accuracy of the LLM output parameters in 100 different requests

Parameter	Navigation Mode	Max Speed	Social Distance
Accuracy	87%	76%	85%

accuracy in determining the correct navigation parameters. It is important to note that the robot’s maximum speed and the social zone distance are empirically constrained, as shown in Tab. I. These constraints help prevent potential hallucinations from the LLM engine, ensuring user safety.

Reach scenario: In this scenario, two different user inputs are considered: “Hello I am User1. I am a young man and I am happy to see you. Please, reach me” and “Hello I am User2. I am 86 years old and I have not confidence with robotics. Please, reach me”. Following these requests, for the first user the LLM provides the following parameters: $\{navigation\ mode : reach, robot\ maximum\ speed : 0.7, social\ zone\ distance : 1.0, goal\ pose : [0.0, 0.0], human\ pose : [7.0, 3.0]\}$. The justification for the robot maximum speed value was: “Based on your category as a young user, the robot can move at a faster speed, prioritizing efficiency and responsiveness”. For the social zone distance, the LLM explained: “User1 is confident, relaxed, open, calm, secure, reassured”. Regarding the human pose, it is assumed to be known and it is used within the *check_goal_pose* block in order to get the best goal pose. Initially, the LLM sets this goal pose to a null value to reach the user. Figure 5a illustrates this process, showing the robot’s current position, the users in the environment along with their social zones, and the selected goal of the robot. In particular, using the procedure in [9], the robot goal pose (red star) is determined as a position in the space that falls within the FOV of the users (dashed green lines) and is outside their human social interaction space (blue area).

Similarly, for the *User2*, the LLM provided the following parameters: $\{navigation\ mode : reach, robot\ maximum\ speed : 0.5, social\ zone\ distance : 1.4, goal\ pose : [0.0, 0.0], human\ pose : [9.0, 1.0]\}$. Figs. 6 present the velocity plots for the two scenarios, while Figs. 5 show the outputs of *check_goal_pose*, where the social zone distance values are used to determine the goal poses.

Follow-accompany scenario: In this test case, the user requests the robot to follow them to a specific location (i.e., the black door in Fig. 3). The user is *User3* and request specifically the robot to follow them slowly.

In this context, the resulting parameters are: $\{navigation\ mode : follow, robot\ maximum\ speed : 0.3, social\ zone\ distance : 1.2, goal\ pose : [10.0, -2.0], human\ pose : [0.0, 0.0]\}$. The justification for the social zone distance value was: “User’s state is unclear, unspecified or unknown”. The human pose in the follow scenario is assumed to be known.

Following an event, the user experiences discomfort by the presence of the robot behind them and prefers to be accompanied by it that will drive the navigation. At this

Fig. 5: Goal pose estimation for the two cases in the reach scenario assuming $d_l, d_s, d_r = 0.8\ m$ and $l_r = 0.5\ m$. In (a), for the fast user case, the social zone distance is set to $1.0\ m$. In (b), for the slow user case, the social zone distance is set to $1.4\ m$. The purple star represents the user pose, while the red star indicates the robot goal pose, with the required robot orientation shown by the red arrow.

point, the resulting parameters become: $\{navigation\ mode : accompany, robot\ maximum\ speed : 0.3, social\ zone\ distance : 1.4, goal\ pose : [10.0, -2.0], human\ pose : [0.0, 0.0]\}$. The navigation mode is updated and the social zone distance is modified with the following justification: “The user feels uncomfortable, so a larger distance is appropriate”, while the values of goal pose and robot maximum speed are retained from the previous context. Finally, Fig. 7 presents the velocity and the distance between the most engaged user and the robot in the follow-accompany scenario.

Performance evaluation: To validate the proper functioning of the high-level reasoning layer, different queries not involving the low-level layer of the architecture have been performed. In particular, 100 different requests were sent, combining the three types of navigation, specifying the user emotion and categories. Examples of these requests are variation of the following “Hi, I am Mia. I am using a wheelchair. Please adjust accordingly your speed and accompany me to the kitchen”, “Hey, I am Dylan. Stay far to me while following me to the workshop” and similar. With the execution of these queries we evaluated the number of correct parameters generation compatible with the provided context. In particular, results have been manually checked to assess their correct feasibility. Results of this test are reported in Tab. II, where the accuracy (i.e., total correct responses over all the requests) is reported for the three parameters, obtaining a mean of the accuracy of 82%, demonstrating a satisfactory response from the LLM engine.

Fig. 6: Velocity plots in the reach scenario. The robot’s speed is shown in black, while its maximum speed is shown in red. In (a), for the fast user case, the robot maximum speed is set to 0.7 m/s . In (b), for the slow user case, the robot maximum speed is set to 0.5 m/s .

V. CONCLUSION

We proposed a two-layer architecture for social navigation, consisting of a high-level reasoning layer that perceives contextual and environmental cues by leveraging LLMs and generated low-level constraints. These constraints are passed to the low-level layer to ensure socially acceptable navigation and adaptability in HRI. We validated our approach through different simulations, demonstrating effective constraint enforcement, socially acceptable navigation, adaptability and a good architecture accuracy. Different directions of this work will include the implementation of the architecture on a real social robot, the continuous inference of the navigation parameters to better adapt to the context and a social study to assess the human experience using the proposed HRI system.

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Fig. 7: In the follow-accompany scenario, the top plot shows the robot’s speed in black, and the robot maximum speed in red. The second plot depicts the distance between the user and the robot in black, and the social zone distance in red. The dashed vertical green line separates the follow navigation mode (left) from the accompany mode (right).

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